

Are Uploads Self?

By Jason K. Resch

This essay aims to justify two conclusions:

1. Computer emulations of brains, when of sufficient detail and fidelity, are equally conscious as biological brains – they experience the same ‘qualia’.
2. If you ‘Upload’ your brain into a computer so that it can be emulated, the resulting conscious states are *yours* – they will be experienced by you.

Are Computer Emulations of Brains Conscious?

To decide whether computer emulations of brains are conscious, and conscious in the same way as biological brains, we will define the set of all possible answers to this question, and then use the process of elimination to arrive at a final answer.

Regarding the consciousness of emulations, there are **four** possible answers:

1. Computer emulations of biological brains are not possible.
2. Computer emulations are possible, but they are not consciousness.
3. Computer emulations are conscious, but not in the same way.
4. Computer emulations are conscious in the same way.

Because these options are so worded to be ‘exhaustive’ we know **at least one** of these options must be true. And because these options are so worded to be ‘mutually exclusive’ then logically **only one** of these options can be true.

So we know the final answer rests in one of the above possibilities.

Let us consider each of these possibilities and what they imply.

Are emulations of brains possible?

Every known physical law is computable. And so it is conjectured, and widely believed, that every finite physical process can be simulated to any degree of accuracy by a computer. This is known as the ‘Church–Turing–Deutsch principle’.

That the brain is a finite system, containing only a finite amount of information, follows from the ‘Bekenstein bound’ which says that physical systems of a finite mass and volume, have a well-defined finite bound on their information.

Given the brain is finite, if all physical laws relevant to the brain’s behavior are computable, it follows that behaviorally-identical emulations of brains are possible.

But some have speculated that the brain utilizes a yet unknown physics that is uncomputable and non-algorithmic. For example, Roger Penrose believes that neurons tap into quantum gravity which Penrose presumes involves uncomputable physics, and therefore neuronal behavior cannot be emulated by any computer.

But Penrose’s idea is discredited by the existence of biologically-accurate ‘neural simulation software’. Such software doesn’t assume any exotic or yet-unknown laws of physics, and yet it can reproduce behaviors observed in biological neurons.

For examples, see:

- ▶ [Scientists Upload Worm's Mind Into a Lego Robot](#)
- ▶ [Openworm Local simulation](#)

These results affirm that the behaviors of neurons and brains are computable. All current evidence points to the computability of the brain and of physics at the scale where the brain operates. Accordingly, we should reject option #1.

Emulations of brains *are possible*. But are they conscious?

Are emulations of brains conscious?

Some philosophers, such as John Searle, suppose that computer emulations of human brains, while possible, would simply not be conscious. Instead they would be so-called ‘philosophical zombies’ – entities that are behaviorally identical to conscious beings, but who are simply not there. There is *nothing it is like* to be one.

At first blush, nothing about the idea of philosophical zombies is obviously wrong. We imagine a being who, by every external impression looks and works the same, and then we imagine just such a thing, only lacking an internal view-from-inside.

But once we begin to think more deeply about the implications that follow, the plausibility of philosophical zombies becomes ever more doubtful.

Given that philosophical zombies are behaviorally identical to their conscious counterparts, it follows that should they be possible, there is no way to tell if your closest friend or family member were a zombie. In fact, everyone else on earth besides you could be a philosophical zombie, and you would never know it.

For zombies supposedly display all the same behaviors conscious humans do:

- They would cry and laugh, and show emotions they don't have.
- They would claim to be conscious, and would show no signs of deception.
- They would recall and describe dreams they had the previous night.
- They would take aspirin for headaches that cause them no discomfort.
- They would lose nothing from anesthesia, and gain nothing upon waking.
- They would get lost in the beauty of a sunset, despite not seeing anything.
- They would describe their own sensations, while never feeling anything.
- They would write books about consciousness, without ever experiencing it.

Such behaviors are strange for something that has no inner life. Can something really ponder the nature of consciousness without being conscious?

Consider a conscious human who suffers from chronic back pain and his hypothetical *zombie twin*. If you asked each to write a paragraph describing exactly how that back pain feels and the manner in which it hurts and distracts from work, each would (owing to their behavioral identity) write word-for-word identical paragraphs describing this pain.

But for the case of the zombie twin, we must ask: where does this information come from? How can the zombie, which has never known pain, discomfort, or ever felt anything for that matter, describe in the same exquisite detail, everything that the conscious human has to say about his pain and how it disrupts his life?

From what source does the zombie get this information? How does the zombie know how to wince in the same way and at the same time as the conscious person?

We are beginning to see some of the problems of zombies.

The notion that we could change nothing about the workings of a brain and yet remove its consciousness, may be as inconsistent as the notion that we could change nothing about the workings of a body and yet remove its health.

Consciousness may be an inevitable and inseparable property of working brains.

Perhaps something about the brain's biochemistry is necessary for consciousness. This was John Searle's position: that the neural circuitry of neurons can host a conscious mind, while the electronic circuitry of silicon transistors cannot.

David Chalmers created a powerful argument against this idea, using the concept of hybrid brains, made partly of organic neurons, and partly of synthetic ones.

Consider then that the 100% organic brain experiences consciousness as brightly and vividly as any normal conscious human does. And if Searle is right, then an entity with a 100% synthetic brain experiences nothing at all – a blank.

But what about the intermediate cases? Does replacing one organic neuron with a synthetic one cause consciousness to blink out? If not, then what happens as we replace another, and another, and so on until a large fraction of the brain is composed of these synthetic neurons?

Chalmers reasons: if by the end state of "0% organic; 100% synthetic", consciousness is eliminated, then there must be some intermediate point at which consciousness is present, but somehow diminished. Colors may be faded, sounds may be muted and less distinct, lights may be darkened, pains may be dulled, etc.

But this leads to a genuine paradox. The person who is at some intermediate stage, will behave exactly the same as before (due to the functional identity between the organic and synthetic neurons), but they will cease to experience things identically.

As this person's rich conscious experience fades away to nothing, at no point do they hint that anything is wrong. He doesn't get dizzy nor ask to be taken to the hospital. Nor does he panic about the fact that he's going colorblind. In fact, if you asked, he would report seeing colors and hearing sounds just as vividly as ever. He would offer no clues of dulled senses, in fact, he would pass all the same tests of sensory discrimination at any stage of replacement.

So here we have a case where a person's *beliefs* about their own states of consciousness are disconnected from the *reality* of their experiences. But how can one be wrong about their own sensations? Consciousness is marked by awareness, but here one remains unaware of even radical changes to their experience. How could there be big changes to one's experience that you couldn't notice?

Searle believed that if this experiment were performed, you would be in a state of "wanting to cry out that you were going blind" but would be unable to, and would hear a voice not under your control report that "everything is fine."

But such an answer is inconsistent. Such thoughts of panic are not supported by any of the organic or synthetic neurons. Being functionally equivalent, the neurons preserve all the same patterns of activity as are found in a fully organic brain. And so, if patterns of neural activity reflecting thoughts of panic don't exist in a 100% organic brain, they can't exist in any hybrid state of organic and synthetic neurons.

Chalmers concludes: "Failing a remarkable, magical interaction effect between neurons and silicon—and one that does not manifest itself anywhere in processing, as organization is preserved throughout—such new beliefs will not arise."

If we reason that radical changes to one's own experience is something that we can notice, report on, and speak out about, then it follows that one's experience must not change at any stage of replacement between 100% organic to 100% synthetic. For if it did, then we would be able to notice it, and speak out about it.

The functional equivalence between the organic and synthetic neurons guarantees we do not deviate in our thoughts or behavior. Accordingly, we can conclude that one's internal felt-experience must not change either from this substitution. What matters to a mind is then, how the brain's parts *behave*, not what they are made of.

Note that the final state of the brain, once it is 100% synthetic, is equivalent to a fully synthetic brain, e.g., a computer made entirely of synthetic materials.

If at no stage does experience become disconnected from the brain's thoughts concerning its experience, then because the thoughts remain unchanged, the experiences must also remain unchanged. Thus we conclude that the consciousness remains unchanged throughout the replacement process.

Emulations of brains *are conscious*. But are they conscious in the same way?

Are emulations of brains conscious in the same way?

Some philosophers, such as Sydney Shoemaker believe philosophical zombies are impossible, and so conclude that a brain emulation must necessarily be conscious. However, Shoemaker makes room to believe in the possibility that two functionally-equivalent minds could have qualitatively different experiences.

For example, might two functionally identical brains, made of different materials, have different kinds of experiences? For instance, could a carbon-based brain experience dandelion flowers as yellow, while a silicon-based brain experiences dandelion flowers as purple? How would we even be able to tell?

The philosopher Arnold Zuboff developed a clever argument against this possibility. Assume that silicon circuits did indeed experience dandelions as purple, where biological circuits experienced them as yellow. Then we could perform the following experiment: replace part of the brain's visual cortex with functionally equivalent silicon circuits, but only for half the visual field. Since each brain's hemisphere processes half of the visual field, this would amount to replacing part of the visual cortex in one hemisphere only, and leaving the other unchanged.

The person who underwent such a replacement would, under the assumption that the silicon circuits result in a different qualitative experience, experience a visual field on one side that was completely normal and unchanged, while the visual field on the other side would look totally strange and different. Perhaps, for example, all of the colors are inverted so that reds look like green and vice versa, and blues look orange, and vice versa, etc. Then when the person awakens from their brain surgery, they might see a vista such as this:

As with the gradual replacement case from before, here we are guaranteed functional equivalency. The silicon circuit visual cortex takes in the same inputs and produces the same outputs as the biological circuitry did. Accordingly, the rest of the brain must respond exactly the same as it did before.

So one must carry on thinking, behaving, and speaking as if nothing is wrong. You would function completely normally; you would not bump into things, you would not stop with awe or wonder at the strange way things now look in half your visual field. You would not complain to doctors that anything was awry.

Zuboff concludes the only way to make sense of this scenario is to accept that there cannot be any qualitative changes to experience without some corresponding functional change. Thus Zuboff concludes “The only way of avoiding that clear absurdity is to accept functionalism as the full account of not just the presence but also the character of qualia.” Chalmers reached a similar conclusion, saying “functional organization fully determines conscious experience.”

This conclusion is aligned with a deeper, and more established principle from computer science: ‘The Church–Turing Thesis’. This is the foundational principle on which computer science is based. It says that every general-purpose computer is

capable of perfectly emulating any other, and hence all general purpose computers are in a sense equivalent.

A corollary that follows from this is: no piece of computer software can ever (with certainty) determine what hardware it is ultimately running on. This is because the program could always be running within a 'virtual machine' that is itself being emulated by a different kind of machine.

So if the brain is something that can be emulated on a computer (as we established by rejecting possibility #1), and if that brain could somehow tell (e.g. by feeling or experiencing something different) when it was running on one type of computer versus another, then that would constitute a violation of the Church–Turing Thesis. Since you then would have computer software (the brain emulation) that can distinguish when its underlying hardware is different.

If the brain could make such a determination, it would reflect as a different series of thoughts, which correspond to different series of computations performed by the computer. Hence, it creates a situation where a given program cannot be run on two different general purpose computers and yield the same result. Such a program represents a violation of the Church–Turing Thesis.

Given Zuboff's argument for why function fully determines the character of experience, and the fact that any counter-example would contradict an established tenet of computer science, we conclude:

Emulations of brains are not only conscious, but conscious in the same way.

So if you upload the state of your brain into a computer, and that emulation is of sufficient detail and fidelity, you can rest assured that the states of consciousness realized by this emulation will be identical with those produced by your brain.

But would it still be you?

Would an Emulation of My Brain still be Me?

With modest assumptions about the brain's computability, then uploading one's mind will at a minimum result in an entity out there that behaves in such a way to carry on one's goals, and who preserves one's memories and relationships.

With a few more assumptions, as we explored in the previous section, we can establish a strong confidence that such an entity will even be conscious in the very same way that you are conscious now. But for most, this is not enough.

What most seek by mind uploading is to *subjectively survive*.

Subjective survival requires more than the mere continuation of some duplicate, and more even than that duplicate enjoying identical conscious states. Subjective survival requires that one actually *survives as* and *becomes* that uploaded mind.

In other words, subjective survival requires that one's *self / I / soul / spirit* continues through that new brain, such that the experiences had by that brain are experiences that *you* will have in a direct, subjective, and first-person way.

To determine what is required for subjective survival, we need to explore a field known as the philosophy of 'personal identity'. This field is primarily concerned with the question: which experiences belong to which persons?

The Limits of Empirical Science

Before we get into the philosophical arguments, it is worth taking some time to see why such arguments are the only path available to progress on these questions.

The reason is that empirical science, being that which is practiced by way of objective experiments, cannot answer these questions in a satisfactory way. This remains true no matter how advanced technology becomes in the future.

Consider the case where we transferred John's biological brain into a functionally-equivalent silicon brain in a new robot body. What we are interested in is whether John's original self has survived the transfer to this new body.

But no matter what question we ask of this robot instance of John, it will (owing to functional equivalence) always give the same answers as had we asked the original John with his biological brain.

If we ask, “Hey John, are you in there?” He’ll answer, “Yes, I made it! I am here.”

If we ask, “Do you still feel like yourself?” He’ll answer, “I feel the same as before.”

If we ask, “But is it the real, original you?” He’ll answer, “Yes, it is me. I survived!”

John’s insistence that he has survived is fully predictable from the mere fact of functional-equivalence between the biological and silicon brains. They behave the same and hence will give the same answers in reply to the same questions.

As long as there is functional equivalence, the uploaded brain will never feel like it is someone else, or that it is not the same person it was before. And because comparing and analyzing behavior defines the limit of what is empirically verifiable, no test can ever hope to expose the result of John’s subjective survival.

Thus, there’s no objective experiment we can perform on John that would convince anyone else that the same “soul of John” as found in the biological brain has continued on in the robot brain. Nor does undergoing the test subjectively provide you with sufficient evidence to determine the answer. You can still wonder, am I truly my original self, or a copy who falsely believes I am the original?

Accordingly, some *leap of faith* is required to make that step, whether it be into an uploading machine, a teleporter pad, or even to undergo invasive brain surgery.

This isn’t to say there aren’t good reasons why one should subjectively survive a body replacement. Rather, it is only to show that such reasons won’t come from empirical science. We must get there by way of rational reasoning and argument.

These are the domain of philosophy.

Questions of Personal Identity

Out of the set of all conscious experiences that will ever exist, which ones are *yours*?

It is a more complicated question than it at first seems.

According to the view assumed by most people (the usual view), there is a special biological body out there linked to “you” and the experiences had by *this particular biological body* (during its life) defines the set of experiences that are *yours*.

But if “the body” and “its life” are what defines one’s experiences, what sorts of changes can the body undergo and still remain *the same* body? And what sorts of events cause a *permanent termination*, rather than a *temporary interruption* of its life?

While the usual view is adequate for everyday purposes, it tends to fold whenever we try extending it to out-of-the-ordinary situations. Consider these examples:

- **Long Coma:** If someone is in a coma for many years, almost every atom in their body is replaced by normal metabolic processes during that time. So the person who wakes from the coma has a different body than the one they had when they were last awake. Do people survive such body transitions?
- **Brain Surgery:** During brain surgery consciousness is discontinuously shut off via anesthesia, parts of the brain are removed, and the person wakes up in a different time and place, and now with a slightly different brain. Does one survive such a surgery, with its discontinuous changes in time, space, and even in the organization of one’s brain?
- **Back from the Dead:** If your body technically dies (e.g. it froze in a cold lake to the point where your heart and brain function ceased), but then later is warmed and resuscitated, do you subjectively survive? Do the experiences of the revived self belong to the same person who existed before they froze?
- **Disassembly & Reassembly:** Consider the case above, except to get you out of the lake your frozen body had to be broken into several chunks so they could be transported to the hospital, where they were put back in order before thawing. The hospital has advanced technology that allows them to still heal and resuscitate your body and restore brain function. Is it still you? Does the number or size of pieces make any difference to your answer?
- **Teletransporter:** Advanced technology allows your body to be scanned in atomic-detail, disassembled, and then reassembled atom-by-atom in an alternate location. Would it still be you? And would it still be you if the destination were to use a different pile of atoms to reassemble your body?
- **Faulty Teletransporter:** Similar to the teletransporter, but this one results in an imperfect copy, perhaps displacing a few atoms here or there, or perhaps losing or implanting a memory or two during its operation. Will it still be

you who emerges on the other end of the transporter? If not, how is the faulty teletransporter different from conventional forms of transport, such as riding a train (during the course of which you will emerge in a slightly different state having gained and lost some memories)?

- **Split-Brains:** in a surgery known as a ‘corpus callosotomy’ the bridge linking the brain’s hemispheres is cut. This results in two independently conscious minds. Does the person who existed before the surgery become neither hemisphere, survive as one hemisphere, or survive as both hemispheres?
- **Quantum Multiverse:** According to some interpretations of quantum mechanics, we exist in a multiverse where all possibilities are realized. Thus in each moment, untold copies of yourself are created. Does your consciousness splinter off and continue along with each of those copies? And if so, are all the experiences of all your future selves experiences you will have, or does this split result in *others* who are not you? For what reasons should these ‘others’ have any less claim to being you, than *you*?

The usual view ties personal identity to the life of a particular biological organism. As such, in situations where it is difficult to define clear bounds for the life of an organism, such as when a life form splits, traverses a discontinuity, or survives or is revived in unfamiliar ways, it is hard to say whether the person *subjectively survives*.

Problems with the Usual View

Aside from its limitations, there are reasons to believe this usual view is wrong.

The first reason is there are deep conceptual problems that stem from the usual view, making it inconsistent as a theory. The second reason is a statistical argument that shows with overwhelming probability, the usual view must be wrong.

Conceptual Problems with the Usual View

We will begin by considering some of the conceptual problems that stem from assuming the usual view of personal identity. The usual view of personal identity holds that one’s experiences are tied to possessing a particular body.

Last Week's Potatoes

The physicist Richard Feynman remarked with some astonishment, how strange it is that new material components constantly enter, stream through, and finally leave our bodies, just as water molecules stream through rivers:

“So what is this mind of ours: what are these atoms with consciousness? Last week’s potatoes! That is what now can *remember* what was going on in my mind a year ago—a mind which has long ago been replaced. This is what it means when one discovers how long it takes for the atoms of the brain to be replaced by other atoms, to note that the thing which I call my individuality is only a pattern or dance. The atoms come into my brain, dance a dance, then go out; always new atoms but always doing the same dance, remembering what the dance was yesterday.”

– Richard Feynman

If we *subjectively survive* our own metabolism—a metabolism that continuously constructs new bodies for ourselves from the food we eat, then the sameness of material can be of no relevance when it comes to one’s subjective survival.

If this principle is general, then whether a new body is made slowly or rapidly, ought make no difference. Should a near-immediate replacement be any different?

A Black Box

The philosopher Thomas Nagel, in his 1965 paper “Physicalism” remarked on a strange fact: no objective physical fact, anywhere in the universe, can be found to indicate the simple fact that *his perspective* is the one confined to the body of the being that goes by the name “Thomas Nagel.”

"Consider everything that can be said about the world without employing any token reflexive expressions. This will include the description of all its physical contents and their states, activities and attributes. It will also include a description of all the persons in the world and their histories, memories, thoughts, sensations, perceptions, intentions, and so forth. I can thus describe without token-reflexives the entire world and everything that is happening in it—and this will include a description of Thomas Nagel and what he is thinking and feeling. But there seems to remain one thing which I cannot say in this fashion—namely, which of the various persons in the world I am. Even when everything that can be said in the specified manner has been said, and the world has in a sense been completely described, there

seems to remain one fact which has not been expressed, and that is the fact that I am Thomas Nagel. This is not, of course, the fact ordinarily conveyed by those words, when they are used to inform someone else who the speaker is—for that could easily be expressed otherwise. It is rather the fact that I am the subject of these experiences; this body is my body; the subject or center of my world is this person."

If there is no physical indication or reason for why Nagel's view (or anyone else's for that matter) is or should remain confined to one particular body, then is this a real limitation? Can anything be "physically done" to a body to make *another person* inhabit it, while the *original person's soul* has been evicted?

Let's consider a hypothetical 'black box' – in the form of a small closet. We can see people enter and leave this black box, but we have no idea what happens inside it.

You see your close friend, Jane enter this black box, close the door, and then emerge, alive and well a minute later. By every physical measure, she is identical to the person who entered moments before. The question is: could anything have happened inside this black box to have destroyed Jane's original self, to have caused Jane to *subjectively die*, and then implant Jane's body with a *new self*?

For example, what if while in the box, Jane's body is taken apart atom-by-atom, those atoms are shuffled around, and then she is put back together atom-by-atom?

The Jane that would emerge would walk and talk just like the original. For all physical particles of the same type are fundamentally 'indistinguishable'. They're not just indistinguishable in practice, but even in theory. From this it follows that it can make no physical difference if someone's atoms are rearranged, or swapped with other atoms of the same kind. The resulting behavior will be the same.

So would the act of momentarily taking Jane apart kill her, while the subsequent reassembly cause an entirely *different self* to emerge? And what could this mean? What exactly is different about the Jane who steps out? As William James said, "A difference which makes no difference is no difference at all."

Trading Places

Let's consider the black box room again, only this time, you see two friends of yours, Jim and Jane, both enter the black box at the same time. Then moments later, you see both of them leave.

The question: Is it possible for the two of them to have switched places, such that Jim's self now occupies Jane's body, and vice-versa?

Case 1:

Upon entering, an advanced nanotechnology begins morphing Jim's body and brain into the state Jane was in upon entering, while at the same time, it morphs Jane's body into the state Jim was in upon entering. At the end of this process, after the transformations, the *physical end state* is Jane's and Jim's bodies as they were when they each entered, but now in swapped locations.

Have Jim and Jane merely swapped positions, or has Jim *become* Jane, while Jane *became* Jim? In this case, if we hold to a notion of bodily continuity, it seems like each has become the other. But we can modify the black box to suggest otherwise.

Case 2:

During the body morphing, for each change, an atom from Jane's body is transported to the location of Jim's, and vice-versa, such that by the end, all of Jane's body's atoms have simply moved by a few feet, and likewise for the atoms of Jim's body. Framed this way, it now seems as though each has merely teleported to the location the other previously occupied.

So instead of presuming one became the other, we now are led to conclude they have only swapped positions. And yet, when they step out of the black box, the physical situation between these two cases is indistinguishable.

Case 3:

To see how hairy problems of personal identity can get, consider a final version of the black box. In this case, upon entering, the black box scans Jim and Jane, disassembles their atoms, shuffles the atoms into one pile, then uses these atoms to reassemble Jim and Jane in each other's former location.

What can we say of who became whom, or where Jim and Jane end up? When they emerge from the black box after having their atoms mixed up, where is the original Jim? Is he in the body that looks like Jim? Is he in some mixed state? Has he been made into Jane? Has he been killed and is now nowhere to be found?

Given the indistinguishability of atoms, it can make no physical difference whether his original, or some mixture of his atoms were used in his reconstruction. All we can objectively say of these cases is:

Two people entered a room, and two physically-identical people left the room, now in opposite positions. But the history of the atoms leaves no trace or mark indicating which of the three cases were performed within the black box. Atoms will, when in the same configuration, always behave the same. The history of a hydrogen atom is irrelevant to how that atom behaves.

How do you Know Who You Are?

This question seems trivial, but it reveals a deep, and often-overlooked fact:

One does not determine who he is by checking some objective fact. For example, you needn't check the ID card in your wallet, or the numbers on your mailbox to know which person (out of all the people in the world) you happen to be.

Instead, we use a much simpler heuristic: you are the person upon which first-person experiences are centered. That is to say, *you* are present in the body that has an immediate and direct feeling of pain when that body's arm is pinched.

But note that this fact is true for all bodies with consciousness. Every body contains within it the experience that it is a privileged "I" constituting a unique center of experience.

So if one doesn't use *objective facts* to determine who one is, and if every subject has the same *subjective feeling* of being an "I", how does one know which person he is?

Are Duplicates Self?

"The idea of such an alter ego seems strange and implausible, but it looks as if we will just have to live with it, because it is supported by astronomical observations. The simplest and most popular cosmological model today predicts that you have a twin in a galaxy about 10 to the 10^{28} meters from here. This distance is so large that it is beyond astronomical, but that does not make your doppelgänger any less real."

– Max Tegmark

We have little trouble imagining the same person existing in the *same place* at *two different times*. And yet, our intuitions struggle to accept the idea of the same person existing in *two places* at the *same time*.

According to our modern understanding of space-time, the dimensions of space and time are interchangeable. Hence, these two situations should be equivalent. If the same person can exist in different times at the same place, then the same person can exist in different places at the same time.

If the technology existed to clone oneself, and have each clone go out and live two different days, then come back at night to re-integrate the memories of the day, this would provide a visceral feeling of having been in two places at the same time.

Such a thing might even be possible to experience with current technology. By anesthetizing the corpus callosum (the bridge between hemispheres) one could induce temporarily the experience of a split brain case. Each hemisphere, falling out of communication with the other, could have distinct experiences. One could listen to a boring lecture while the other listened to a symphony. A few hours later, when the anesthetic wears off, the formerly separate memories become accessible to the whole brain, and it would seem to that brain, that it had been in two distinct places, having two distinct experiences, at the same time.

Conscious States: A Type or a Token?

Related to the question of duplicates, is the ‘type–token’ distinction.

To get a feel for the distinction, consider a particular *type* of story, say, the novel *Moby Dick*. Regardless of the materials on which it is printed, or the font face the publisher used, every instance of *Moby Dick* is in a sense, the same, in that it consists of the exact same story: all copies contain the same words put in the same order.

However, every hardcopy book containing the story of *Moby Dick* is a unique *token*. No two copies are exactly the same. Aside from particular differences in the detail of manufacture, each copy occupies a distinct place in space and time.

Are *states of consciousness*, better conceived of as tokens, or types?

That is, are “identical states of consciousness” all the same type, regardless of the unique conditions under which they appear—much like how *Moby Dick* is the same story whenever it occurs? Or is each identical state of consciousness like a book copy: distinct on account of its unique time, place, and conditions of occurrence?

Note that from the internal first-person perspective, the view from the conscious state itself, no outer distinctions can be made. In other words, identical states of consciousness all *feel the same*—from the inside.

According to leading cosmological models, our big bang was caused by a process known as 'cosmic inflation'. But cosmic inflation never stops. Once started, it continues to create new big bangs in new places, forever.

On a long enough time line, it is inevitable that in the far far distant future, long after this universe has died, there will be another big bang which by chance is exactly like the one that precipitated our universe. And so, it will develop the same galaxies, stars and planets. One of these planets will be just as Earth is now, with the same population of people, including yourself now as you read this sentence. Will that identical person, with an identical history and having lived an identical life be you? Or does the fact of it being a later universe mean it will be someone else?

Since this later conscious state exists in an identical brain, on an identical planet, in an identical universe, there are not even any objective facts on which a distinction can be made for these two minds. For all intents and purposes they are the same.

So on what basis could we say that this far far future instance is not you?

Bodily Continuity or Psychological Continuity?

The usual view of personal identity comes in two common forms. In the first, emphasis is placed on the continuation of a particular *material body*. In the second, emphasis is placed on the continuation of a particular *psychological process*.

Those who emphasize the **material body** say:

- You can *subjectively survive*:
 - Invasive brain surgery
 - Partial and even total memory loss (amnesia)
 - Personality changes
 - Morphing into a completely different person
- But you *subjectively die* from:
 - A long term coma during which your body is metabolically replaced
 - A teleportation to another location
 - Destructive mind uploads into a robot brain and body
 - Having your body assembled from a different pile of atoms

Those who emphasize the **psychological process** say:

- You can *subjectively survive*:
 - A long term coma during which your body is metabolically replaced

- A teleportation to another location
- Destructive mind uploads into a robot brain and body
- Having your body assembled from a different pile of atoms
- But you *subjectively die* from:
 - Invasive brain surgery
 - Partial and even total memory loss (amnesia)
 - Personality changes
 - Morphing into a completely different person

Which of these is right?

Might each theory be right for the cases in which they predict survival, while each theory is wrong for the cases in which they predict death? If so, the result is a theory more widely permissive of survival.

According to this **permissive-survival theory**:

- You can *subjectively survive*:
 - Invasive brain surgery
 - Partial and even total memory loss (amnesia)
 - Personality changes
 - Morphing into a completely different person
 - A long term coma during which your body is metabolically replaced
 - A teleportation to another location
 - Destructive mind uploads into a robot brain and body
 - Having your body assembled from a different pile of atoms

“This is also the resolution of the tension between the rival criteria for personal identity, psychological and bodily continuity. [...] Either side of the classic debate has the upper hand when it argues positively that the person could remain the same if its own pet criterion was maintained even if the other was wholly absent. And, indeed, one could easily imagine a person going along into another body with a transfer to that body’s brain of his pattern of memories. And yet one can also easily imagine the person’s continuing in the same body with an experience of amnesia or false memories.”

– Arnold Zuboff

This does seem a better fit for our intuitions. We can imagine losing memories, or having false memories implanted, and surviving that. Likewise, we can imagine a mind’s survival by copying its patterns of thought and memories to a new brain.

A Probability Argument against the Usual View

Having reviewed some of the conceptual problems with the usual view of personal identity, we will now review a probability argument, which is definitive in showing the usual view (despite its intuitive appeal) cannot be correct.

The Hotel of Countless Rooms

To introduce the reasoning, we will start with a closely related thought experiment, involving a ‘Hotel of Countless Rooms’. In this hotel, there are countless rooms, and each contains a person who is sleeping. Each sleeper is assigned a randomly generated 1,000-bit “security code.”

Then, a fair coin is tossed 1,000 times to create a 1,000-bit sequence.

One of two games will then be played, either an *Easy Game*, or a *Hard Game*.

In the *Easy Game*: all sleepers are awakened.

In the *Hard Game*: only the sleepers whose “security code” matches the sequence of 1,000 coin flips are awakened, the rest remain asleep forever. Note the odds of any one particular sleeper’s code matching the sequence of coin flips is 1 in $2^{1,000}$.

Question:

Assume that you are one of the sleepers in the hotel of countless rooms, and you find that you have been awakened. Can you infer from the fact of your awakening that it is *overwhelmingly more likely* that the *Easy Game* was played, rather than the *Hard Game*, given the extraordinary luck required to awaken in the *Hard Game*?

The Difficulty of Being Born under the Usual View

What was required for you to exist?

According to the usual view, your existence was unalterably tied to winning an unimaginably long series of what we could call “sperm cell lotteries.”

This requirement in the usual view would have made your existence *absurdly* improbable.

Sperm Cell Lotteries

We can quantify these odds.

To have been born according to the usual view, required that in your conception a specific sperm cell, out of some 200 million sperm cells, reached the egg first.

These odds are roughly equivalent to winning a national lottery.

But it gets worse.

For your “lottery” to have been possible, both your mother and father had to win sperm cell lotteries of their own. The odds of you and each of your parents having won is then 1 in (200 million)³ or 1 in 8 septillion (an 8 followed by 24 zeros).

The usual view, with its requirement of a specific material body, makes your existence extraordinarily unlikely. But the improbability doesn't end with your parents. It required a series of improbable events stretching back to a time before the dinosaurs. If we consider just your 37 most recent ancestors, we obtain a probability approximating 1 in $2^{1,000}$; akin to winning in the *Hard Game*.

But there is an alternative theory of personal identity that ensures your existence. It is akin to the *Easy Game* in the Hotel of Countless Rooms.

“It is enormously more probable that your existence—your awakening to consciousness—had not depended on an absurdly improbable matching of actual winning sperm cells to the sperm cells that were required for you to emerge in a game as hard as the usual view of personal identity.”

– Arnold Zuboff

According to this theory of personal identity, you required neither a specific set of atoms nor a specific set of genes to be born and awaken as a being in this universe.

But this leads to a shocking conclusion: you will experience life as *every conscious being* born to every set of parents.

This alternative theory of personal identity is known by various names. It is called ‘universalism’ by Arnold Zuboff, and ‘open-individualism’ by Daniel Kolak.

If this theory is right, then the question “Would an emulation of my brain still be me?” becomes trivial: *you live as all emulations of your brain*, and also as all emulations of others’ brains, and also as all conscious beings born anywhere in this universe, or for that matter, as any being born in any universe across reality.

Three Theories of Personal Identity

As defined by Daniel Kolak, there are three high-level categories of theories when it comes to theories of personal identity:

1. **Empty Individualism:** the Parfit / Anattā view of personal identity, each ‘person’ is nothing more than a single distinct observer-moment.
2. **Closed Individualism:** the usual view of personal identity, persons consist of collections of observer-moments grouped by some criterion.
3. **Open Individualism:** the Zuboff / Vedānta view of personal identity, all observer-moments are mine because they are all experienced as ‘I’.

These theories divide along how they organize ‘observer-moments’. An observer-moment is a conscious experience confined to a moment in time.

Empty Individualism

Theories under the “empty individualism” category, consider the idea of a person spanning more than a single observer-moment to be an illusion.

Empty-individualism theories posit that a person is nothing beyond a *single conscious experience* fixed in a single moment in time. Hence, the you-from-5-seconds-ago is a different person than you are now, and you-now shall always be only in this single moment of time, and cannot expect to ever experience the future you-5-seconds-from-now. Ideas similar to this can be found in some Buddhist teachings.

In a visual representation of empty individualism, personal borders (dark blue lines) surround each distinct observer-moment (blue circle):

Closed Individualism

Theories under the “closed individualism” category say that each person is defined by a set of *some, but not all, conscious experiences*. The way the borders are defined depends on the details of the particular theory. Some posit that continuity of the body is key, others proclaim that psychological continuity is what matters. Still others, presume that some measure of similarity or closeness is required.

The *usual view* of personal identity is an example of closed individualism. Such theories have been defended by John Locke and Robert Nozick.

In a visual representation of closed individualism, personal borders (dark blue lines) surround collections of distinct observer-moments (blue circles):

Open Individualism

Theories under the “open individualism” category say that *all experiences* belong to you, a *universal subject*, and that personal borders are illusions stemming from a lack of integration of memories and experiences between brains.

Unlike the usual view, which holds that some kind of bodily or psychological continuity is needed, open individualism theories say neither continuity nor similarity are necessary for survival. Ideas similar to this are found in some schools of Hinduism, and it has been defended by Daniel Kolak and Arnold Zuboff.

In a visual representation of open individualism, the personal borders (dark blue line) surround a collection that includes all observer-moments (blue circles):

How Theories of Personal Identity answer the Survival Question

Having reviewed the three theories of personal identity, we can now use them to answer the question of whether or not one *subjectively survives* a mind upload.

Theory of Personal Identity	Do you survive a mind upload?
Empty Individualism	No. You are only an observer-moment. Future states, such as a post-upload version of yourself, constitute other observer-moments, who are not you.

Closed Individualism (Bodily Continuity)	It depends. If you upload your mind destructively, and discontinuously, you die. However, a gradual, in-place, continuous substitution of biological neurons with silicon ones might permit an upload by maintaining bodily continuity.
Closed Individualism (Psychological Continuity)	Yes. So long as the uploaded mind is a faithful representation of your psychological state (memories, thought patterns, personality, etc.) you will find yourself surviving as an upload.
Open Individualism	Yes. You survive as the uploaded mind even when it is not a perfect or faithful copy.

Given the overwhelming probabilistic evidence favoring open individualism, we can have high confidence that the self is preserved through mind uploading.

Further Reading

- **Theories of Consciousness**
 - Zuboff, Arnold. "[What is a mind?](#)" (1994).
 - Chalmers, David J. "[Absent qualia, fading qualia, dancing qualia.](#)" (1995)
 - [Functionalism](#) on Wikipedia
- **Theories of Personal Identity**
 - Zuboff, Arnold. *Finding Myself: Beyond the False Boundaries of Personal Identity* (2025).
 - [Open individualism](#) on Wikipedia